

Studies on Biologically Active Heterocycles. Part-V¹. Synthesis and Biological Activity of Heterocyclic Azadienes and Phosphate/Thiophosphate Derivatives of 1,3,4-Oxa- and Thiadiazoles

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Manuscript received 28 January 1991, revised 30 October 1991, accepted 3 July 1992

Various 2-amino/substituted-amino-1,3,4-oxa/thiadiazoles and their Schiff bases have recently received significant importance because of their diverse biological properties². In continuation our interest in the chemistry of heterocycles³, new Schiff bases (5, 6) and their phosphate and thiophosphate derivatives (7–10) were synthesised and evaluated their antibacterial and insecticidal activities. Their structural assignments were based on physical and spectral data.

The required 2-amino-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxa/thiadiazoles (3, 4) were prepared by the reaction of 2,4-dichlorobenzohydrazide⁴ (1)⁵. 5-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-iminobenzylidene/substituted-benzylidines (5a–g) were prepared by the reaction of 3 with appropriate araldehydes. Similarly, 5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-iminobenzylidene/substituted-benzylidines (6a–g) were prepared from 4 (Scheme 1). The phosphates (7, 9) and thiophosphates (8, 10) were prepared by the action of *O,O*-dialkyl phosphoryl chloride or *O,O*-dialkyl thiophosphoryl chloride respectively, in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetone⁶. Physical and spectral data are given in Table 1.

Compounds 5 and 6 were screened for antibacterial activity against *Bacillus cereus*, *E. coli* and *B. megatarium* QMB 1552 using agar plate diffusion technique⁶. The results show that compounds 5c, d and f are highly active and compounds 5e, g, 6c, d and f are moderately active.

Compounds 7–10 were screened for their insecticidal activities (solution of compound in acetone) against *Drosophilla melanogaster* Maigen by residual film evaporation method⁷. The median lethal concentration values (LC₅₀) of these compounds were established using probit analysis⁸. The results show that all the compounds are active.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries on a Buchi oil heated apparatus and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237B spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) on a Varian T-60 spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal reference.

5-(2,4-Dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxa/thiadiazol-2-iminobenzylidenes (5a–g, 6a–g). *General method*: A mixture of 3/4 (0.01mol) and araldehyde (0.01 mol) was refluxed in ethanol (50 ml) in presence of 2 drops of piperidine for 2 h. The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and the resulting solid on cooling, was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Scheme 1

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5–10*

Compd. no.	R ¹ /R	Yield %	M p. °C	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹	δ^{\dagger}
5a	C ₆ H ₅	81	205	1 630, 1 610, 1 030	6.9–7.4 (m, ArH), 6.5 (s, =CH)
b	4-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	90	195	1 630, 1 610, 1 025	3.3 (s, OCH ₃), 6.7 (s, =CH), 6.8–7.5 (m, ArH)
c	2-(OH)C ₆ H ₄	89	198	3 400, 1 635, 1 610, 1 030	6.3 (s, OH), 6.7 (s, =OH), 6.8–7.5 (m, ArH)
d	2,4-(OH) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	92	208	3 400, 1 630, 1 615, 1 030	6.6 (s, =CH), 7.2–7.6 (m, ArH)
e	3,4-(OCH ₃)(OH)C ₆ H ₃	87	200	3 400, 1 630, 1 615, 1 030	3.2 (s, OCH ₃), 6.3 (s, OH), 6.8 (s, =CH), 7.0–7.4 (m, ArH)
f	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	91	188	1 640, 1 620, 1 030	6.8 (s, =CH), 7.1–7.6 (m, ArH)
g	CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	82	190	1 635, 1 615, 1 030	5.8 (m, =CH), 6.7 (s, =CH), 7.1–7.6 (m, ArH)
6a	C ₆ H ₅	84	222	1 645, 1 600, 630	6.2 (s, =CH), 7.2–7.4 (m, ArH)
b	4-(OCH ₃)C ₆ H ₄	92	255	1 645, 1 595, 630	3.4 (s, OCH ₃), 6.8 (s, =CH), 7.3–7.6 (m, ArH)
c	2-(OH)C ₆ H ₄	84	212	3 300, 1 650, 1 610, 680	6.9 (s, =CH), 7.3–7.7 (m, ArH)
d	2,4-(OH) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	86	214	3 270, 1 650, 1 610, 675	6.5 (s, OH), 6.8 (s, =CH), 7.2–7.6 (m, ArH)
e	3,4-(OCH ₃)(OH)C ₆ H ₃	81	214	3 300, 1 650, 1 610, 680	3.4 (s, OCH ₃), 6.4 (s, OH), 6.9 (s, =CH), 7.3–7.6 (m, ArH)
f	4-N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₄	90	209	1 660, 1 620, 690	7.0 (s, =CH), 7.4–7.8 (m, ArH)
g	CH=CHC ₆ H ₅	79	208	1 665, 1 610, 680	5.9 (m, =CH), 6.8 (s, =CH), 7.2–7.7 (m, ArH)
7a	CH ₃	50	—	1 080	3.8 (6H, d, <i>J</i> 14 Hz), 6.9–7.6 (m, ArH)
b	CH ₂ CH ₃	55	—	1 080	1.4 (6H, t), 4.3 (4H, q), 6.8–7.6 (m, ArH)
c	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	63	—	1 060	0.9 (6H, t), 1.7 (4H, q), 4.0–4.5 (m, 4H), 6.8–7.5 (m, ArH)
8a	CH ₃	52	—	750	3.6 (6H, d, <i>J</i> 14 Hz), 6.7–7.6 (m, ArH)
b	CH ₂ CH ₃	60	—	780	1.2 (6H, t), 4.2 (4H, q), 6.9–7.5 (m, ArH)
c	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	65	—	760	0.9 (6H, t), 1.6 (4H, q), 4.0–4.5 (4H, m), 6.8–7.5 (m, ArH)
9a	CH ₃	45	—	1 080	3.8 (6H, d, <i>J</i> 13 Hz), 6.7–7.6 (m, ArH)
b	CH ₂ CH ₃	50	—	1 080	1.3 (6H, t), 4.3 (4H, q), 6.8–7.5 (m, ArH)
c	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	55	—	1 060	0.9 (6H, t), 1.7 (4H, q), 4.0–4.5 (4H, m), 6.5–7.3 (m, ArH)
10a	CH ₃	50	—	750	3.6 (6H, d, <i>J</i> 13 Hz), 6.8–7.5 (m, ArH)
b	CH ₂ CH ₃	52	—	750	1.3 (6H, t), 4.4 (4H, q), 6.8–7.6 (m, ArH)
c	CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₃	60	—	760	0.9 (6H, t), 1.7 (4H, q), 4.1–4.6 (4H, m), 6.7–7.5 (m, ArH)

*All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analyses. **Compds. 7–10, gummy mass.

[†]Drops of pyridine-d₅ (in 5a–f, 6a–f) and CDCl₃ (in 5g, 6g, 7–10) added for clear solution.

O,O-Dialkyl phosphate/thiophosphates of 2-amino-5-(2,4-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxa/thiazoles (7–10). *General method*: To a mixture of 3/4 (0.01 mol) in acetone (50 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.38 g, 0.01 mol), was added *O,O*-dialkyl phosphoryl/thiophosphoryl chloride (0.01 mol) slowly under stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h till the reaction was complete (tlc monitoring). Solvent was then removed and chromatographed over silica gel using benzene as eluent. The phosphate derivatives (7–10) were obtained as viscous mass after removing the eluent.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Dr. J. N. Baruah,

Director, Regional Research Laboratory, Jorhat, for permitting one of the authors (M.M.D.) to carry out research work in the laboratory. They are also indebted to the Analytical Division of this laboratory for providing spectral data. Authors are thankful to Mr. P. R. Bhattacharya of this laboratory for insecticidal screening.

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NOTES

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